

Regulating Vehicle Access
for improved Livability

D2.9 – Report

Future ready guidelines

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Summary sheet

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Abstract	The aim of this deliverable is to provide guidelines to help cities navigate in the many uncertainties associated with future trends of the transport system while improving liveability using UVARs. It serves as a support for cities in adjusting their policies to be better prepared for these trends. The future ready guidelines build upon the knowledge and experiences acquired from deliverables 2.7 as well as 2.8. Both deliverables analysed emerging trends in the transport system, one focusing on identifying new technologies related to UVARs while the other assessed ReVeAL's pilot cities' future readiness for these trends. The guidelines feeds into the online Decision Support Tool and support European cities beyond the consortium.
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List of acronyms

UVAR	Urban Vehicle Access Regulation
IoT	Internet of Things
LTZ	Limited traffic zone
ZEZ	Zero Emission Zone

About ReVeAL

ReVeAL – Regulating Vehicle Access for Improved Liveability – is a CIVITAS project funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. The goal of ReVeAL is to add Urban Vehicle Access Regulations (UVAR) to the standard range of urban mobility transition approaches of cities across Europe. The overarching mission of the project is to enable cities to optimise urban space and transport network usage through new and integrated packages of urban vehicle access policies and technologies. Such policies can lead to fewer emissions, less noise and improved accessibility and quality of life, which especially benefits the people living in these cities. These policies can also encourage more sustainable transport choices, enabling cities to become more liveable, ultimately healthier, and more attractive for every member of society. To this end, ReVeAL combines conceptual work and case study research with hands-on UVAR implementation in six pilot cities, as well as systematic stakeholder interaction through professional communication activities.

Different UVAR measures have been developed, implemented, and tested in the cities of: Helmond (NL), Jerusalem (IL), London (UK), Padova (IT), Vitoria-Gasteiz (ES) and the project leader Bielefeld (DE). Apart from these cities, the project partners are Ghent University (BE), Università di Padova (IT), POLIS (BE), Rupprecht Consult (DE), Sadler Consultants (DE), Transport for London (UK), TRT (IT), V-Tron (NL) and WSP Sweden (SE). The project started in June 2019 and runs for 42 months.

ReVeAL looks at a range of UVAR measures, both established and cutting-edge approaches, grouped under the three Measure Fields: 1. Regulatory Measures (areas that are regulated by rules, e.g., where only vehicles emitting zero emissions, or low emission are permitted or a traffic limited zone). 2. Spatial interventions (access regulations based on area planning and design, and physical interventions in the public realm) and 3. Pricing aspects (financial charging for accessing specific areas).

Description of the deliverable

Deliverable 2.9 is part of task 2.6 – *Future proofing UVARs* which is one of the main activities of the *Reviewing UVAR options and scenario building* work package (WP2). The task is carried out in two parts:

- **Innovation Observatory report and city-specific readiness assessment:** The observatory covers both mobility products and services (their market penetration and potential transportation and societal impacts) as well as the potential of new technology (its potential business models). Key suppliers and developers have been consulted. With the knowledge gathered during the design phase in task 2.4, the Task Leader performed an assessment of the resilience of each city's regulatory policies and measures. The assessment covers existing policies, those under consideration and potential transition schemes and possible future adaptations.
- **Future-ready guidelines:** These are an extract and generalised practice-based lesson from both desk research and the pilot cities. The guidelines feed into the online Decision Support Tool and support European cities beyond the consortium.

Deliverable 2.9 is part of the latter task – future ready guidelines. The purpose of this deliverable is to construct guidelines helping cities navigate in the many uncertainties associated with future trends of the transport system while improving liveability using UVARs. It serves as a support for cities in adjusting their policies to be better prepared for these trends. The work of feeding the guidelines into the online Decision Support tool has already begun.

Method

The process of developing the guidelines was carried out in three steps:

- Identifying trends that could eventually affect the transport system.
- Risk and opportunity assessment of the trends.
- Based on the experiences acquired, formulation of guidelines helping cities become future ready.

The point of departure for the future ready guidelines is the knowledge and experiences acquired from deliverables 2.7 as well as 2.8. Both deliverables have analysed and identified emerging trends in the transport system. Deliverable 2.7 has focused on new technologies related to UVARs while deliverable 2.8 has assessed ReVeAL's pilot cities' future readiness regarding current and emerging trends. Furthermore, deliverable 2.8 has assessed the risks and opportunities of emerging trends on a more general level in relation to different types of UVARs by a resilience matrix.

Results

This chapter aims at presenting the findings of the project. Firstly, emerging trends are described, and thereafter risks and opportunities are assessed with regard to UVARs. The analysis of risks and opportunities will lead to the last section of this chapter, the future ready guidelines.

Emerging trends

The transport system is in constant movement. Simultaneously as vehicles move humans and goods, technological developments, as well as general societal trends, are shifting the characteristics of the transport system. There are many uncertainties associated with the future of mobility, hence, it is important to study potential outcomes to be future ready.

Societal trends

Deliverable 2.8 examined ReVeAL's pilot cities' readiness for future uses of UVARs by assessing the resilience of regulatory policies and measures concerned with future trends in society and the transport system. In earlier stages of the ReVeAL project, future trends possessing inherent features to possibly affect the effectiveness of UVARs have been identified. The identified trends span from climate change and future pandemics to future technologies enabling a society based on gig economy or a transport system constituted of shared mobility. Presented below are some identified trends that could change the behaviours of how we use the transport system.

- **Future pandemic:** As seen in the current COVID-19 pandemic, pandemics can affect the usage of different modes of transport as well as trip types and frequencies. Transport involving critical equipment and humans is affected by a pandemic, as well as the need for safe transport in perspective of the spread of infection.
- **The gig economy:** Trend towards a more flexible form of employment that most likely would generate new transportation patterns and usages of infrastructure in the cities.
- **E-commerce:** Increased deliveries emerging from e-commerce require new ways of planning for transportation and deliveries within cities. More transportation of goods to one's private door affects the whole logistics chain.
- **Climate change:** Climate change affects all systems on the globe, including transportation. Increasing consciousness and more political measures will put pressure on a change in the transportation system. The rapid shift to electric mobility is an example of a political response to climate change.
- **Aging population:** Changed accessibility needs and increased home-based services will affect the need for different adapted modes of transport.
- **Higher or lower travel demand:** Different circumstances, such as these mentioned above, can and will affect travel demand. Other circumstances could impact travel demand, such as economic development or new ways of travelling – e.g., shared mobility or ride-hailing.
- **New technology:** Technological developments are enabling new transport opportunities. For instance, connected vehicles have the potential to report current traffic conditions, and fully autonomous vehicles give car access to a larger group of the population.

The last trend of new technology has been explored in detail in Deliverable 2.8, which is summarised in the following section. As seen, future outcomes are uncertain and depend on the magnitude of the trends mentioned above, as well as the trends' interdependencies between each other.

New technology

Deliverable 2.7 explored how new technology can affect the use of UVARs – new UVARs as well as improvements of existing UVARs. The work on Deliverable 2.7 drew up a framework for new technology associated with UVARs consisting of *Facilitators*, *Influencers*, *Enhancers* and *Contributors*:

- **Facilitators** comprise technologies *in vehicles and infrastructure* that can affect the UVAR landscape in that they can create both the opportunity to develop UVARs and the necessity to execute new UVARs.
- **Influencers** comprise digital technologies *more broadly* that can affect the implementation and possibilities to develop new UVARs.
- **Enhancers** are conceptualised as tools that are not linked to a specific technology that bring with them new opportunities to support, steer and monitor compliance and allow for new ways of managing existing UVARs and implementing new UVARs, and are complemented by information to and from users.
- **Contributors** constitute more specific measures for governance and monitoring that can contribute to the effectiveness, implementation and support of and need for UVARs, complemented by information to and from users.

The development of influencers, enhancers and their applications in facilitators and contributors are generating interesting opportunities for the development of UVARs. An influencer that has generated many opportunities recently is connectivity. Connectivity can be used in geofencing activities and, in extension, as an enforcer. Moreover, connectivity technologies enable the Internet of Things (IoT) services if sufficient vehicles and infrastructure are connected. IoT can in turn be used for automation processes and contributors enabling dynamic traffic management and data sharing services. Influencers and facilitators are in general more driven by market or military forces, by a curiosity about technology, while contributors are shaped by an interaction of market forces and political ambitions.

The conclusions on the work related to new technology are that relevant tools already seem to exist on the market. However, the way in which the technologies enter and influence the market depends on political as well as market forces. This depends largely on political acceptance, technological advancements as well as financial conditions. Regulations could facilitate the diffusion of new technologies. For instance, regulations aimed at protecting inhabitants' integrity can alleviate users' concerns about privacy in the context of big data collection. Other regulations defining common standards for digitalisation and management of traffic rules support the use of certain tools. Regulations do, in turn, require common understandings and definitions. However, setting specific requirements and rules might be challenging as different technologies often overlap with each other or are interdependent.

Risks and opportunities

The development of new technologies and rising societal trends such as the ones described above come with new risks and opportunities for cities. Future trends may in general weaken UVAR strategies, potentially diminishing their relevance or soundness over time. A few of those risks and opportunities have been assessed as part of the work performed under task 2.6 – deliverable 2.8. The present chapter aims at highlighting the main ones, identified under each of the ReVeAL measure fields – spatial interventions, pricing aspects and regulatory measures (see Appendix 1 – Measure fields and building blocks for a full description of the measure fields). The guidelines developed in this report will then aim at guiding cities in developing UVAR programs which are a better fit to face those risks or make the best use of those opportunities.

Spatial interventions

Spatial interventions, usually aimed at reallocating space away from car traffic to cycling, walking or public transport have been implemented in many cities of the world, including in all the ReVeAL pilot cities. Interventions aimed at facilitating and promoting walking and cycling are more sensitive to climate change than those encouraging non-active modes. Some places will become warmer, others will experience longer winters. This means that one can expect more temporal and seasonal variations in cyclist volumes. Cities should monitor this development and analyse any changes in the conditions for cyclists and other users of micro-mobility. Spaces could be designed in a way that provides flexibility to adapt to changing circumstances and needs. In the meantime, climate change increases the need for and relevance of such spatial interventions. These measures are also highly resilient to some of the future trends identified in the ReVeAL work, such as future pandemics. Indeed, the Covid-19 pandemic saw a large decrease in the number of daily trips and a large share of the remaining trips shifted to individual modes. As commuters needed to travel less, public transport was negatively impacted while individual travel modes such as cycling gained relevance and attractiveness, enabling better physical distancing with active modes of travel. Spatial interventions that increase space for walking and cycling are therefore relevant in a future pandemic situation.

In addition, physically restricting access may impact some crucial street users such as emergency transports or mobility of critical staff. Yet, the demand for such services may increase in the future (e.g., increasing risk of disasters and pandemics). Spatial interventions must be designed to allow safe passage for emergency vehicles and critical staff.

A higher number of deliveries in a future where e-commerce significantly grows may also increase the need for UVARs to manage the use of public spaces. Spatial restrictions in the city would need to be balanced with the ability for stakeholders to carry out the deliveries that are needed efficiently – for example, if there were a special exemption on cycling and pedestrian streets for delivery vehicles, how should it be designed, and for which types of vehicles? The reduction of parking opportunities also risks leading to situations where delivery vehicles park randomly and overcrowd streets when making stops. Dedicated parking alternatives e.g., logistic bays, already implemented in some of the ReVeAL pilot cities, could help mitigate such an issue. A global strategy may be developed at city scale to efficiently and more sustainably manage logistic systems as a whole.

Physical access restrictions also raise the question of accessibility of certain areas to populations with reduced mobility, including the elderly who may move around less easily. In a situation where the population is ageing, the need for accessing or parking close to local amenities may increase for a higher number of people and spatial restrictions may need to better adapt or compensate for those specific

groups. It is necessary to make sure that infrastructure giving priority to cyclists and/or pedestrians is suitable for other ability-giving vehicles as well.

Finally, fast changes in technologies may lead to the emergence of new ways of travelling. The supply of shared services such as micro-mobility or car-pooling has increased over the years thanks to new systems allowing easy deployment, operations and use. Freed-up urban space may be reallocated towards drop-off parking zones for those new services.

New technologies such as geofencing would enable restrictions like traffic bans to be enforced in new ways: vehicles being controlled by software and no longer by drivers if autonomous vehicles enter the market for instance. Many restrictions could be processed through the vehicle itself instead of through the eyes and mind of the driver. However, enforcing such measures would require automation to some degree.

Risks

- With climate change and changing weather conditions, one can expect more temporal and seasonal variations in cyclists and pedestrians volumes. Cities should monitor this development and analyse any changes in the conditions for these users. Spaces could be designed in a way which provides flexibility to adapt to changing circumstances and needs.
- The reduction of parking opportunities risks leading to situations where delivery vehicles park randomly and overcrowd streets when they stop. Yet, the demand for such services may increase in the future (e-commerce boom). Spatial measures may be adjusted to allow deliveries to be performed efficiently while not impacting other road users.
- To not impede emergency services, spatial interventions must be designed to allow for the safe passage of emergency vehicles.
- Limited space available for shared transport services while fast changes in technology lead to a rapid increase in the supply of such services (autonomous vehicles, IoT etc.) Risk: inadequate space distribution.
- The ageing population increases the need for close access to amenities, sometimes not compatible with spatial restrictions. It is necessary to make sure that infrastructure giving priority to cyclists and/or pedestrian is suitable for other ability-giving vehicles as well.

Opportunities

- Spatial interventions such as drop-off zones or delivery hubs could help mitigate some of the risks identified above and could be considered when designing new projects.
- New technologies such as automation and geofencing can complement spatial measures and facilitate their enforcement (speed reduction, shared traffic zones and pedestrian priority, etc.).
- New technologies can replace some of the spatial interventions, providing the same benefits with more flexible systems which could be better adapted to changing needs. However, such systems will often require the adaptation of vehicles or systems in place

Pricing measures

Pricing measures aim at discouraging non-sustainable transport by charging motorists a fee for their trips or to park. Such measures have proven their effectiveness in many cities of the world, but their effect may diminish, or they may even be counter-productive in given future situations.

Time-based pricing measures for instance may become more difficult to implement and have less impact in a future where commuting patterns are less extreme, less reliable and traffic peaks smoothen over time (Gig Economy, work anywhere culture, etc.). Such trends have been observed following the Covid-19 pandemic, as working no longer systematically requires one to commute daily to an office. As technologies – especially IT – evolved, many employees have been and are now able to work remotely. The Covid-19 pandemic showed that this was not only functioning but also that employees wished to change working habits, many deciding to keep working remotely at least a few days a week even after a drop in the severity of the pandemic. Generally, these trends may increase the need for dynamic measures, such as dynamic traffic control, or for flexible systems that can be adjusted if commuting traffic peaks smoothen over time.

Pricing measures based on emissions may also have less impact in a future where car users switch from fossil-fuel cars to electric ones. If the goal of pricing measures is only to reduce emissions, the general trend of electrification may indicate that the measures have succeeded in encouraging motorists to switch to electric vehicles. If the city additionally expects other effects (e.g., a decrease in traffic volumes), a rapid electrification of the car fleet would make emission-based pricing measures less relevant, as these vehicles would not be affected by the measure.

Pricing measures also ask the question of equity and how to not increase inequity in different future scenarios. Those most affected by pricing measures are those with the lowest income. Unless pricing measures are based on income levels, they will have a different effect on different economic groups, meaning that some will simply be forced out, while pricing won't mean much to those at the higher end of incomes.

The impact of pricing measures may also decrease or even have undesirable effects in scenarios where autonomous vehicles enter the market. Indeed, to avoid paying fees, self-driving vehicles would probably be parked where fees are low. Vehicles may drive many empty trips (empty re-positioning driving). Measures would need to be adjusted to limit such an effect. Pricing measures may also be less relevant or more difficult to enforce in a scenario where shared mobility increases, as the question could be raised of who should be paying the fee – since vehicle owner and passengers will often not be the same person or household, passengers sharing the same vehicle may not know each other, etc.– pricing measures would need to be adapted so that the pricing structure is clear.

New technologies such as geofencing or IoT would improve and facilitate the development and enforcement of pricing measures.

Risks

- Time-based traffic measures: risk to see traffic peaks smoothening over time, reducing the impact of such pricing measures. Travel patterns also become less reliable, making it harder to define a fixed time range under which the measure should apply (need flexible systems).

- Electrification will reduce the impact of measures based on emissions if the measure aims to reduce the number of cars running in the public space and not just encourage motorists to switch to electric cars.
- Pricing measures affect higher and lower income groups differently, meaning that they will not have the same behavioural effect, thereby putting the low-income group under higher pressure to comply than the high-income group.
- In the case of augmentation of autonomous vehicles and shared services: pricing measures risk encouraging vehicles to drive more empty trips to avoid paying e.g., parking fees or time-based charges. As a result, the UVAR might become irrelevant and counterproductive.

Opportunities

- New technologies such as geofencing or IoT would improve and facilitate the development and enforcement of pricing measures. However, it would be crucial to design them according to the city's goals and consider their impact on deliveries, critical staff, and the elderly.

Regulatory Measures

Regulatory Measures, like Zero-emission zones or limited-traffic zones, aim at restraining access to certain areas for given types of vehicles, emission levels, or trips. In a future where e-commerce increases, and hence if the number of deliveries increases, such measures may become harder to implement without hindering the efficiency of deliveries to households. In the meantime, a higher number of deliveries may increase the need for UVAR to control the services. Regulations for vehicle type/dimensions and emissions could for instance largely influence the choice of vehicle fleet used. It is therefore crucial to have a large-scale strategy in place and design the regulations to match the goals of the city (e.g., many small delivery vehicles or fewer large ones, etc.).

In a more general way, regulatory measures ask the question of who should be granted access or not, and how to regulate this. Here as well, access restrictions may need to adapt to certain types of population, such as the elderly who may move around less easily. In a future situation where the population is ageing, the need for access to local amenities may increase for a higher number of people. Critical staff may also need to move around freely in exceptional situations such as pandemics. All of the latter show a need for traffic regulation schemes which can easily adapt to changing population patterns and needs.

Finally, and as with emission-based pricing measures, ZEZ and LEZ may have less impact in a future where car users switch from fossil-fuel cars to electric cars. If the goal of such measures is only to reduce emissions, ZEZ and LEZ are relevant and may encourage more motorists to switch to electric vehicles. However, if the city expects other side effects, such as a decrease in traffic volumes, a rapid electrification of the car fleet would make these regulations less relevant, as they may still allow for the number of vehicles driving in the area to remain the same or even increase.

Risks

- With a growing share of vehicles being low or zero-emission, ZEZ's have less of an effect on lowering traffic numbers.
- Restraining access for motor vehicles directly impacts services highly depending on such travel means, e.g., delivery services. Yet, the demand for such services may increase in the future (e-commerce boom). LTZ may be even more relevant if the number of delivery vehicles running in the streets increases, to limit their number or keep areas free of them. However, the right spatial measures should be found to allow the work to be performed.
- ZEZ/LTZ may risk hindering critical staff mobility (increasing risk in case of a pandemic).
- The ageing population increases the need for close access to amenities. This may be difficult to address in ZEZ/LTZ regulated by emissions or vehicle type/dimensions which are only based on vehicle characteristics.

Opportunities

- New technologies such as geofencing or IoT would improve and facilitate the development and enforcement of such measures. However, it would be crucial to design them according to the city's goals and consider their impact on deliveries, critical staff, and the elderly.

Future ready guidelines

Based on the identification of emerging trends and what risks and opportunities are involved with those trends, with regard to different types of UVARs, future ready guidelines have been formulated. The guidelines can be divided into six comprehensive sections, which span from scenario planning to flexible systems and societal impacts.

Scenario planning

A vital process for cities to be future ready is to analyse the impacts emerging trends in transport systems may have. The structures of society, and in turn the travel behaviours, are shifting faster today than historically due to the fact and tendency that the world is becoming more and more connected. For instance, the COVID-19 pandemic has rapidly and to a great extent changed people's travel behaviours. Thus, cities need to plan and be prepared for different scenarios depending on emerging trends' nature.

In accordance with the work process in Deliverable 2.8, WSP¹ has in a separate project from ReVeAL drawn up a framework for decision-making for alternative futures, to prepare different stakeholders to become future ready. The framework is based on five key steps:

Trend Analysis: research and exploration of trends, according to impact and certainty.

Scenario Generation: development of scenarios from anchor points based on known and perceivable trend interactions and relationships (see Figure 1).

Implications for Action: screening of opportunities and challenges of the generated scenarios.

Validation with Experts: consultation with experts across several disciplines to validate the implications of the scenarios.

Resilience Analysis: assessment of proposed policies or solutions.

To conclude, the future is by no means deterministic, there are many uncertainties involved with the outcome of the future. In order to, in a resource-efficient way, tackle the uncertainties and prepare for the future, cities should plan for different scenarios to some degree. Notably, the future can depend on inherent attributes of the cities, e.g., location and demographics, hence, the diffusion power of one trend can diverge in different cities and countries. Thus, the scenario planning needs to be city specific to some extent depending on the interdependencies of the trends.

Figure 1. Scenario generation step in the scenario development process. (Figure source: WSP)

¹ WSP, 2018. Decision-Making for Alternative Futures: Applying Scenario Planning to create resilient strategies in a time of rapid change. Part 1: scenario development. Available at: <https://www.wsp.com/en-qa/services/system-dynamics>

Guideline – Scenario planning

Define a framework helping the city cope with uncertainties associated with the spread of emerging trends in society. The framework could include processes such as trend analysis, scenario generation based on diffusion levels of emerging trends, identification of challenges and opportunities with alternative scenarios, as well as resilience assessment of proposed policies and solutions concerned with the challenges and opportunities.

New technology and problem definition

During the last decades, there have been several technological stepping stones, such as connected vehicles and infrastructure, enabling new transport opportunities, both in terms of vehicle development and traffic management. A certain area that has been developed is the collection and analysis of big data through the development of connectivity technologies, often referred to as IoT, enabling new data services for the cities to use in their mobility planning. As mentioned in the risks and opportunities assessment, if designed to the city's specific goals and demographic setting, new technology could help the cities understand the transport patterns and be a good tool for traffic management. However, new technology can become obsolete for the specific city's needs and be costly, both in terms of financial and human resources.

Ideally, cities should define the challenges it is experiencing today as well as future probable challenges. This mapping should form the basis of what new technology and services the cities should use. New technological developments, such as analysis services of big data, enable new possibilities to regulate traffic, however, it is important for cities to clarify and evaluate how a specific product or service can meet the city's needs, today and in the future (see also UVAR's success is dependent on public acceptance, thus, communication and cooperation with the public can strengthen the implementation of UVARs.).

However, from our experience, cities do not always have the resources to widen their perspective and assess how different services might, or might not, help meet their needs. Cities could share their experiences and cooperate to be able to allocate more resources to prepare for the future.

Furthermore, it is important to acknowledge that while new technology can facilitate the implementation and management of UVARs, new regulations may be needed, e.g., restrictions of where a fully autonomous vehicle can park in a city while minimising the vehicle kilometres.

Guideline – New technology and problem definition

Identify challenges the city is facing as well as probable future challenges. Evaluate what opportunities new technology has in meeting these challenges. New technology might require plentiful resources. Use new technology where it will improve the situation.

Flexible systems

Most of the risks identified earlier in the report show a need for UVARs to adapt more easily to different types of users and trends. By using more flexible technologies, one reduces the risk of being "stuck" with systems which no longer fit the needs or objectives of the city. Spatial interventions consisting of heavy

infrastructure work can be quite inflexible and difficult to adapt, requiring heavier investments and time. New technologies can replace some of the spatial interventions, providing the same benefits with more flexible systems. However, such systems will often require parallel adaptation – e.g., adapted vehicle equipment – which may be a limitation and also comes with a certain cost.

Furthermore, technology and trends are moving fast and systems may rapidly become obsolete. London realised this when analysing a geofencing system to regulate a ZEZ. The system considered would have required hybrid vehicles to switch to electric mode in defined zones. Yet, the latest trends and policies are showing that a fully zero-emissions future is possible sooner than previously thought. Therefore, the municipality changed its objectives to now strives for fully zero emission transport rather than to develop a technology to regulate hybrids. It would not be viable to invest in a system which works for hybrid vehicles when now striving for zero emissions.

Adopting a stepwise approach could be a way to limit the risks of getting “stuck” with obsolete or dysfunctional systems, by implementing UVARs first in pilot areas, assessing their effectiveness and suggesting corrective actions, if necessary, before expanding them.

Guideline – Flexible systems

- Make use of more flexible technologies whenever possible.
- Keep in mind that technology and trends are moving fast, and that systems may rapidly become obsolete.
- Take a step-by-step approach to limit risks at implementation stages and monitor the UVAR effectiveness early in the process before risking getting “stuck” with non-functioning systems.

Monitoring and evaluation

The resilience level of UVARs to future trends is to some extent today based on assumptions. Over time, there is a need to observe how UVARs react to rising trends. Monitoring and evaluation aim at supporting that.

Indeed, the implementation of new UVAR measures, in particular when they rely on new technologies on which perspective and feedback still lack, requires close follow-up, monitoring and evaluation via continuous collection and analysis of data, statistics and user feedback, during and after implementation. Only by controlling how measures perform can one make sure they have the desired effect, that they fit user needs and rising trends, that they progress towards the objectives and goals of the city, and if not, suggest corrective actions.

By providing regular information to decision-makers and other stakeholders, monitoring also helps demonstrate the validity of the measures. Monitoring is, more globally, an important tool in the communication process with stakeholders and the public, who may not be familiar with new measures yet, serving more transparency and allowing information-based decision-making. Bielefeld, for instance, pointed out how helpful it had been to collect data (noise, air pollution, number and satisfaction of customers, sales) before and after the implementation of UVARs in the city, to make the discussion more

objective and to be able to illustrate the advantages of different solutions, measure their success, and increase acceptance².

Monitoring and evaluation activities should be conducted on a regular cycle, although the frequency might vary with evaluation taking place at a longer time interval. Clear monitoring and evaluation procedures should be developed at early stages. They should outline the key evaluation and monitoring questions and describe how, which and when monitoring activities will be carried out, who is responsible for them, what resources will be necessary and who will participate.³

Guideline – Monitoring and evaluation

- Establish a clear monitoring and evaluation procedure when developing UVAR programs and strategies.
- Collect and evaluate data, statistics, and user/stakeholder feedback during and after the implementation of UVAR measures to make sure they fit new needs and trends rising over time. Monitoring and evaluation are especially relevant when using new technologies on which perspective and feedback are still lacking.
- Suggest corrective actions if needed.

Cooperation, communication, and information

Cooperation between cities or coordination actions from higher instances could be an alternative to how cities can allocate resources to be able to evaluate new technology and become future ready. By communicating lessons and experiences, common standards and evaluation frameworks can be drawn up. With such cooperation actions, cities do not have to evaluate each new technology individually but can rather focus on the implication a certain new technology would have on traffic planning and traffic management. Metaphorically speaking, cities do not have to reinvent the wheel all the time. Cities like Helmond and Jerusalem, for instance, highlighted how beneficial the international cooperation was in the ReVeAL project. They pointed out that the experience allowed them to exploit the knowledge and experience at hand in other places and deepen their knowledge by site visits and peer reviews from other – sometimes more experienced – cities⁴. Common standards can be set on multiple levels; regional, national, and international, e.g., by EU projects. However, for common standards to be relevant for the cities they should be interpretable to be city specific and there should be some enforcement controlling. If cities are not following the regulations, there should be some noticeable consequence obliging them to be progressive with regard to UVARs. In general, cities are most inclined to follow regulations when there exists a local context to the regulations, e.g., if the regulation is national.

An UVAR's success is dependent on the public's acceptance of it, thus, communication with the public is also essential to ensure the soundness of UVAR measures. By getting regular feedback, one can more easily identify and understand user needs coming with changing trends and new technologies (see also

² Bielefeld, city report, February 2021

³ Similar to recommendations on monitoring and evaluation of SUMPs. See also CH4ALLENGE project, Monitoring & Evaluation Kit. Available at: <https://www.eltis.org/resources/tools/sump-monitoring-evaluation-kit>

⁴ Helmond, city report, February and August 2021. Jerusalem, city report February 2021

UVAR's success is dependent on public acceptance, thus, communication and cooperation with the public can strengthen the implementation of UVARs.). Understanding public opinion, based on an active two-way dialogue, is also crucial for a successful implementation process, fostering acceptance of the public to measures they may not yet be familiar with.

Guideline – Cooperation, communication, and information

Share knowledge and experiences with UVARs by cooperation with other cities and/or authorities, to implement new or improved UVARs in a resource-efficient way.

UVAR's success is dependent on public acceptance, thus, communication and cooperation with the public can strengthen the implementation

Societal impacts

Depending on the characteristics of different UVARs, the influence UVARs have on different groups of society can differ. To create a city enabling all groups of the society to take an equal part in mobility it is important to consider how different groups of the society could be affected by different trends and solutions.

Equality

Gender, age, income, race, and plenty more can affect how one is affected by UVAR. The future will bring changed demographics and most likely also a search for a way to design more just cities. When aiming to design a just city from a transport perspective, it is important to keep in mind that travel is not only commuting. As an example: women have different travel patterns than men. Since they often perform a greater share of care duties within the household, women combine their daily commuting with more maintenance trips in comparison to men⁵. Kids and the elderly have different travel patterns than the working part of the population, while income can also affect where you live, as well as how you travel.

In terms of designing just cities and transport systems, this means that one can not only focus on commuter corridors and peak hours when deciding how and what part of the transport system to develop. This also goes for UVARs and the building blocks within ReVeAL. Some UVARs might affect some groups of people unduly. This should be assessed, to ensure that actions can be taken to minimise the negative or unjust effect.

New technology

New technological developments are often more expensive than conventional technology, at least until they reach cost parity. Even when cost parity is met, some demographic groups of the society will have it more difficult to take part in the new technology. When planning for the implementation of future UVARs

⁵ Ng, Wei-Shiuen. Acker, Ashley. 2018. Understanding Urban Travel Behavior by Gender for Efficient and Equitable Transport Policies.

or improvements of existing UVARs using new technology, it is important to consider that all members of the society can equally use the public space of transport.

Transitional period

As transport innovations do not automatically tackle the larger structural patterns within socio-economical contexts, UVARs alone cannot handle the task of achieving equity within the transportation system. To avoid transferring and replicating the same inequalities when designing and restructuring, existing power asymmetries need to be addressed early in the process of transition. New technology will not automatically be more inclusive and equal than the systems they replace.

A fair and just transition is, therefore, necessary from a social perspective. This can be implemented by recognising aspects such as geographically equal prioritisation and equal participation in decision-making procedures. Different economic and social conditions express themselves to a large extent in decision-making and implementation. Transitions tend to be top-down driven, which constrains citizens' abilities to affect the development of their local community. Engaging local stakeholders and marginalised citizens during the transition are critical to achieving the full potential of new technology.

Another crucial thing is the question of access, which preferably should be controlled through policies and political instruments. Especially the cost of new technologies is a key consideration that is a potential barrier. It's also relevant to consider equity in the transition regarding prioritisation from a larger regional, national and global perspective. Every city has its difficulties and opportunities; thus, every city needs different measures for the transition to be realised.

Guideline – Societal impacts

1. Assess which groups might be unduly affected by the UVAR
2. Ensure that actions are taken to minimise the negative effects to groups unduly affected by the UVAR. Analyse whether there is a need for a transitional period.
3. Undertake stakeholder engagement to assess the issues and fears associated with the UVAR and address them in planning
4. Design UVARs that not only focus on commuting but plan for connecting journeys and activities related to care.
5. Make sure to be aware of perceived safety, which can vary among different groups of people (based on gender, abilities, age, race and more).

Conclusions

To conclude this report, the future is uncertain and depends on how emerging trends are received in a city's specific context. Furthermore, the future will depend on the societal integration of trends along with the interdependencies between the trends. In order to be future ready and prepare for a city using UVARs while enhancing the overall liveability, the city needs to be flexible. The presented guidelines can be summarised as follows:

- A city needs to plan for different scenarios consisting of different combinations of trends and the likelihood of these trends.
- New technologies are creating new opportunities as well as risks in the UVAR landscape. Identify which challenges the city is facing and evaluate whether new technologies can help meet these challenges.
- Monitor and evaluate implemented UVAR measures to enhance the experiences and knowledge on how to successfully use UVAR to improve livability.
- Cooperate with other cities and stakeholders for resource-efficient implementation of UVARs.
- As highlighted, the future is by no means deterministic, having flexible systems constituting the UVAR scheme will benefit the success rate of implemented UVARs.
- The transport system is a crucial part of society and is used differently by different groups in society. Assess how planned UVARs can affect different groups and plan for a just and equal transport system.

To sum up, due to the many uncertainties involved with the future, it is difficult to advise cities with concrete guidelines. Future readiness is fundamentally a figure of thought together with educated guesses on how likely certain trends and compositions are. However, cities have some power to determine some trends' insertion in society, e.g., regulations of new technology, thus, it is important to have visionary goals and work together for the desired tomorrow.

Appendix 1 – Measure fields and building blocks

Building blocks are UVAR measures that have been defined as part of the ReVeAL process under each Measure field. The building blocks as of May 2022 are presented in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. building blocks under each Measure Fields and complementary measures, defined as part of the ReVeAL process

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